

USE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING.

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Abstract: This article provides information on the rational use of modern innovative technologies in teaching English, which is one of the world's languages, and the use of proven teaching methods.

Key words: Innovative technology, methodology, beginning, identifier, lexicography, syntax, Methodology

Language is the main means of communication, without which it is difficult to imagine the existence and development of human society. Today, at a time when there are great changes in social relations in our world, communication media (information technologies) require the improvement of students' communicative skills, they can exchange ideas in different situations during interaction with other participants of communication, language and so It is necessary to use the norms of behavior correctly. In such conditions, the main purpose of a foreign language is the formation of communicative skills, that is, it is required to carry out interpersonal and intercultural communication in a foreign language.

At this stage of school education, there are important changes that cover almost all aspects of the pedagogical process. They set specific goals and objectives for the educational process. One of its main tasks is to improve the teacher's pedagogical skills by mastering modern teaching and learning technologies. With the use of any new technologies, new pedagogical ideas of the teacher begin: the clarity of the systematic, methodological language, the emergence of clear tactics in the teaching methodology. Competency - professional level... The speaker communicates freely on various topics. Feels confident in debates and discussions, knowledge is close to the level of a native speaker. At this stage of learning the language, a quick orientation to the new language is the state of the language on various topics. Working with text is also about relying on context. The proficiency level includes writing detailed tests on specific topics with correct use of terms, grammatical structures and punctuation. Description of different methods of teaching English. It is the most relevant and intensive method of language learning in the modern and rapidly changing world. Today, the consumer can choose training for any taste - English for lawyers, English for economists, business English,

etc. With this approach, listeners are given a lot of formulaic phrases and clichés. Yes, it gives you the opportunity to orient yourself in a work environment, but is the language base and language sense really formed? This question remains open. Linguistic-social-cultural method of language learning. This method is a systematic approach aimed at studying the cultural and social environment without the goal of "dry" acquisition of lexical features and grammatical constructions. Linguistic-social-cultural method raises the veil of stylistic coloring and vitality of language. Two verbs, to do and do, are good examples. Their main difference is that the verb make means a creative approach to business, thoughtful actions. The most important task of the educational process is the student's personal interest. It is necessary to know which technologies should be used in the educational process to obtain the planned results. It is clear that the use of any specific educational technology, no matter how perfect, does not create the most effective conditions for determining and developing students' skills. The purpose of this method of language learning is for the student to be able to understand the interlocutor sufficiently, to feel the specific features of the language from the point of view of culture and ethics. Communicative method of learning English. This approach is most common during the period when various language courses and trainings appeared. Real training manuals are designed to use this technique only. Using this method works very well abroad. The use of advanced pedagogical technologies, interactive, innovative methods, communicative and informational tools is required in the process of teaching foreign language classes. In our republic, new methods and requirements have been developed in accordance with the recommendations of the European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR) for foreign language teaching and assessment of knowledge and skills of foreign language teachers. According to it, textbooks were created for students of general education schools and vocational colleges. In accordance with these requirements, classrooms were equipped with stands and new information and communication techniques. The demand for learning a foreign language is increasing day by day. Foreign language science is divided into four aspects (reading, writing, listening and speaking), and separate concepts and skills are given for each of them. The conclusion is that the students of the course actively participate in the process and learn to perceive foreign speech. Speaking and listening take up most of the learning time. This method involves the artificial recreation of the language environment. The purpose of the communicative method is to help students overcome the language barrier, to teach the participants of the course to speak the language first, and then to think in this language. This gives the

teacher the opportunity to plan the teaching of different groups of students / learners with different needs, knowledge levels and worldviews.

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